

Economic Aspects of Nanyaseik Area, Kachin State, Northern Myanmar

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Abstract

Nanyaseik area is situated in Hpakant Township, Kachin State (Northern Myanmar). It is bounded by North Latitudes (25° 36' - 25° 43') and East Longitudes (96° 30' - 96° 36') in one inch topographic map index of 92C/10. The total areal coverage is about 130 square kilometers. The rock sequence of the study area consists of medium to high grade metamorphic rocks and intrusive igneous rocks. Gemstones are found as detrital fragments in gem-bearing soil horizons known as byones. These gems include precious ruby, sapphire (including padparadscha) and others; spinel, tourmaline, zircon, quartz, diopside and almandine garnet. Moreover, placer gold extraction is also dispersed throughout the Nanyaseik area. Placer golds at Manaw, Sabaw, and Warphu villages and compact ultramafic rocks for use as construction and building materials are of economic interest. Therefore, the Nanyaseik area is economically important for our country.

Keywords: Nanyaseik area, byones, placer gold, ultramafic rocks.

Introduction

Nanyaseik area is situated in Hpakant Township, Myitkyina District, Kachin State (Northern Myanmar). It is bounded by Latitudes 25° 36' to 25° 43' N and Longitudes 96° 30' to 96° 36' E in one inch topographic map index of 92 C/10. The total areal coverage is about 130 square kilometers of mountainous and rugged terrain (Figures 1, 2, 3).

Chhibber (1934b) examined the stone tract of Nanyaseik in the Myitkyina district, where rubies were first discovered in the neighborhood of the Kammo Hka north of Nanyaseik (25° 37' 11" N, 96° 35' E) in the early nineties. Nanyaseik stone tract lies some 80 km west of Myitkyina and 19 km west of Kamaing. He also described the major localities as being in the neighborhood of Mawthit and Marrawmaw, where there were about 100 men would work for rubies and other gems by digging on the Twinlone and Loodwin systems, in the midst of a dense jungle and Shan women would wash for gold. In addition to ruby, spinel is also found. Their colour was said to vary from a near-opaque, dark green to a bright, translucent red, with the latter colour being rare. Metamorphosed limestones were through to be the source of origin for both the rubies and spinels.

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Figure 1. Location Map of Nanyaseik Area

Figure 2. Satellite image of the Nanyaseik Area

Figure 3. Geomorphology of the Nanyaseik Area
(Three dimensional view)

Scope and Objectives

The present research aims to -

- (a) Study the representative rocks and gem occurrences from Nanyaseik Area.
- (b) Prepare a fairly detailed geological map of Nanyaseik Area.
- (c) Mention the possible economic aspects.
- (d) Study the quality of gemstones in comparison with those of Mogok Stone Tract in the hope of gaining attention to mineralogists, gemmologists, geologists, other gem dealers and gem collectors.

Methods of Study

Field Study

- (a) A detailed geological mapping for Nanyaseik Area.
- (b) Systematic collection of samples of various representative rock types to carry out petrological studies.
- (c) Minerals and gems sampling for detailed mineralogical and gemological studies.

Laboratory Techniques

- (a) Detailed petrographic studies were made from representative samples of various rock units and individual minerals. Some unknown minerals were identified by X-ray diffractometer (XRD).
- (b) Chemical composition and trace elements of representative rock types were determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) method.
- (c) Identification of precious and other precious gemstones were carried out with the aid of gemmolyte, microscope, refractometer, polariscope, spectroscope and other available gem testing instruments.

Workable Gem Worksites and their Related Gemstones

Gem Worksites

In Nanyaseik area, the workable gem worksites are mostly situated in the western environs of Nanyaseik village. These worksites are generally N-S trending. Mine area extends about 8 km in NS, 5 km in EW directions. Based on the field evidences, rubies and other gemstones in Nanyaseik area are originated in marbles, and associated igneous rocks. However, gemstones are extracted from byones, secondary deposits (gravels) rather than from insitu (primary deposits). According to the recent field investigation, there are five gem worksites can be listed below:

1. Khaing Kyin worksite (N 25° 41' 34.2" / E 96° 32' 25.1")
2. Lakha worksite (N 25° 38' 42.2" / E 96° 33' 17.6")
3. Warphu worksite (N 25° 38' 25.8" / E 96° 32' 59.4")
4. Sabaw worksite (N 25° 39' 38.1" / E 96° 32' 52.9")
5. Manaw worksite (N 25° 37' 25.5" / E 96° 32' 44.5")

Essential products of these gem worksites are primarily ruby and other semi-precious stones like spinel, tourmaline, sapphire, garnet, zircon, quartz, diopside, etc are also extracted. The above gem worksites work under the authority of Myanmar Gem Enterprise, Ministry of Mines. Annually workable period is only in dry season because of the heavy rainfall and swampy conditions in rainy season.

Khaing Kyin Worksite

The Khaing Kyin worksite is situated the northern most part of the study area. At there, Ko Naing (local people) used a square pit mining method, locally called Lebin twin (N 25° 41' 34.2" and E 96° 32' 25.1") (Figure 4). The depth may be twenty five feet and the outcome products are only red coloured gem materials (Figure 5). The workable period is about five months and production rate is about thirty carats.

Figure 4. Photo of Lebin Twin

Figure 5. Photo of ruby crystals

Lakha Worksite

The Lakha worksite is besides of Warphu worksite. In this worksite, local people (Ko Ahpha) used a open pit mining technique, locally called Inn bye method (Figure 6). In this worksite, ruby and other assorted gems are got from secondary deposits (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Photo of Lakha Worksite

Figure 7. Photo of ruby crystals

Warphu Worksite

The Warphu worksite is near Lakha worksite. The two working mine companies are Sai Khay Company (N 25° 38' 25.8" / E 96° 32' 59.4") and Hlan Hlann Company (N 25° 38' 29.7" / E 96° 32' 36.0"). The above two working mine companies also used the open pit technique. At Sai Khay worksite, they showed some ruby and other gems (Figure 8). During my field trip, Hlan Hlann Company got a ruby crystal from byone at this time of investigation (Figure 9).

Figure 8. Photo of ruby crystals from Sai Khay Worksite

Figure 9. Photo of a ruby crystal from Hlan Hlann Worksite

Sabaw Worksite

The Sabaw worksite is the central part of the Nanyaseik area. The office of Myanmar Gem Enterprise, Ministry of Mines is situated at Sabaw village (N 25° 39' 38.1" / E 96° 32' 52.9") (Figure 10). There are four mine companies circulated in Sabaw village namely: Myat Noe San Eain Company (N 25 ° 39' 35.6" / E 96 ° 32' 45.2"), Aung Lan Nagar Company (N 25 ° 39' 30.6" / E 96 ° 33' 16.2"), Gem City Company (N 25° 39' 33.6" / E 96° 33' 11.2") and Myanmar Htun Company (N 25° 39' 17.8" / E 96° 33' 04.6"). All of these mine companies used the open pit mining method.

Depending on my field data, Tetlone Htoe Kyin (N 25° 39' 43.0" / E 96° 32' 53.3") at Sabaw village produced by forty pieces per day and the working time is about eight hours (Figure 12). Notably Gem City worksite produced a lot of carbolate crystals and other semi-opaque assorted gems (Figure 11). Sabaw worksite is fruitful of assorted gemstones and also crowded with local and economic people than the other area in Nanyaseik.

Figure 10. Photo of the office of Myanmar Gem Enterprise, Sabaw village

Figure 11. Photo of ruby and assorted crystals from Gem City Worksite

Figure 12. Photo of a ruby crystal from byone at Tetlone Htoe Worksite

Manaw Worksite

The Manaw worksite is situated the southern most part of the study area. Local people said that it was the first appeared famous worksite before the discovery of Sabaw worksite. There are three workable mine companies in Manaw village namely: Lwe Nguu Phwan Company (N 25° 37' 21.3" / E 96° 32' 41.7") (Figure 13) , Zabu Kyaw Aung Company (N 25° 37' 07.1" / E 96° 32' 50.1") (Figure 14) and local people U Sai Maung Kwe worksite (N 25° 39' 30.6" / E 96° 33' 16.2") respectively. These mines also applied the open pit mining technique.

Figure 13. Photo of ruby crystals from Lwe Nguu Phwan Worksite

Figure 14. Photo of ruby crystals from Zabu Kyaw Aung Worksite

Gold

Gold is the unforgettable mineral of Nanyaseik area and can be found at transported soil. The occurrences of transported gold can be classified as alluvial and eluvial deposits which are accumulated in shallow or deep depressions. Some places are covered with thin overburden of eluvial deposits. Some are covered with thick overburden of alluvial deposits. But the accumulation of gold is not regular. Gold occurrences are associated with quartz detritus (auriferous) in the lateritic soil. The regular applied methods are panning and sluicing for collecting free gold. At Tetlonehtoe Kyin (N 25° 39' 43.0" / E 96° 32' 53.3") of Sabaw village the alluvial gold are occurred (Figure 16). At Zabu Kyaw Aung worksite (N 25° 37' 07.1" / E 96° 32' 50.1") of Manaw village alluvial gold 1 ywe per day and 10 days collected (Figure 15). This gold quality is about (20 – 22) K. At Sai Khay worksite (N 25° 38' 25.8" / E 96° 32' 59.4") of Warphu village, gold particles can be studied on Inwine. (Figure 17).

Figure 15. Photo of gold from
Zabu Kyaw Aung Worksite

Figure 16. Photo of gold specks from
Tetlone Htoe Worksite

Figure 17. Photo of gold specks from Sai Khay Worksite

Decorative Stones and Industrial Materials

In Nanyaseik area, vast amount of decorative stones, industrial and constructional materials are extracted from marbles, gneisses, serpentinite and granite (Figures 18 and 19). Because these rocks are hard in compact, homogenous texture and less fractured.

Figure 18. Photo of road stone from
serpentinite outcrop

Figure 19. Photo of industrial
materials from gneiss outcrop

Discussion and Conclusion

Actually, Nanyaseik area is wealth in economic mineral deposits, especially ruby, spinel, tourmaline, quartz, zircon, sapphire (padparadscha), garnet, diopside, gold and other decorative stones and industrial materials including construction and building materials. All varieties from Nanyaseik area are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels). These have been transported, deposited and accumulated in the adjacent valleys and flat lowland areas. Gold occurs as placer deposits at Manaw, Sabaw and Warphu villages. Granitic rocks in the study area can be used as construction and building materials and marbles, when pure can be carved as statues or even baked for lime.

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